

"Hold-up in" Non-isothermal Flow in Thermal Field Flow Fractionation

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An expression for retention ("hold-up") of solute in thermal field flow fractionation is developed. The dependence of the retention on magnitude and sign of the Soret coefficient (σ) of the solute and the applied temperature gradient is deduced and discussed therefrom. Poor retentions reported by various workers for macromolecules in aqueous systems has been explained on this basis.

FIELD flow fractionation (FFF) is an analytical technique, designed to achieve separation of macromolecules. In this method, a lateral field of some kind is coupled to a non-uniform axial flow to induce differential migration of macromolecules present in a mixture. The external field applied to solute zones in a channel forces each zone towards one wall where the latter forms a narrow layer of unique thickness. Then the laminar flow, as initiated along the channel, and the differential flow profile carries the zones downstream at different velocities depending on the degree of penetration of the solute layer into faster streamlines towards the centre of the channel. The unequal zone-velocities lead directly to separation along the channel or separation in elution sequence¹. The method resembles chromatography in having separation achieved by differential migration along a narrow tube through which the liquid is flowing but differs from chromatography in that the separation occurs in a single-phase system and does not involve a two-phase distribution system and also that it needs the application of an external field.

This external (lateral) field may be thermal, electrical, centrifugal etc., or a suitable combination of these. In thermal field flow fractionation (TFFF), a temperature gradient applied across a narrow channel through which the solvent is flowing retards the downstream progress of macromolecules. The retardation results from thermal diffusion of the macromolecules which thereby concentrate in the vicinity of one wall (usually the cold one) of the channel and are thus forced into low velocity regions. The differential retention of various macromolecules stems directly from the magnitude of such thermal diffusion effect for each macromolecular solute.

In the present paper, an expression for retention (or "hold-up") of a solute in such non-isothermal

flow in a channel will be developed and the dependence of the effect on magnitude and sign of thermal diffusion parameters of the solute and the applied temperature gradient will be discussed therefrom.

Let us consider a homogeneous solution of uniform concentration \bar{C} entering a narrow channel of depth $2a$ at a_1, a_2 (Fig. 1) and flowing in a laminar fashion through the region A under isothermal conditions with a uniform velocity of \bar{u} cm/sec. Let the solution pass to the non-isothermal regions (B+D) and flow under the influence of an applied

Fig. 1

temperature gradient (in the x direction) $\Delta T/2a$, across the channel. $\Delta T/2a$ is assumed to be constant everywhere in B and D. Let the region B be the one in which the non-uniform concentration profile under thermal diffusion (Soret effect) builds up, while in region D (of length L) let the concentration gradient be fully developed and become time-invariant (steady state).

Regions B and D form part of a rectangular duct of height $2a$ and width b (Fig. 1). We ignore region B in this calculation although it is of possible interest for determining the isothermal diffusion coefficient of the solute(s).

In region D, the steady-state concentration distribution of the solute has been shown to follow an exponential relation

$$C = C^{\circ} \exp(-x/l) \quad \dots (1)$$

given by Giddings *et al*³ where C° is the concentration at the cold wall [which is taken as origin, $x=0$, vide Fig. 1, and x in eq (1) denotes the distance from the cold wall; according to this origin, the centre-line of the duct is at $x=a$], and l is the "Characteristic thickness" of the solute layer (at the cold wall). l is given³ by

$$l = 1 / \left(\frac{\alpha}{T} + \gamma \right) \frac{dT}{dx} = 1 / (\sigma + \gamma) \frac{dT}{dx} = 1/k \quad \dots (2)$$

where $k = (\sigma + \gamma) \frac{dT}{dx} \quad \dots (3)$

Here, α is the thermal diffusion factor of the solute and is equal to σT , σ being the "Soret coefficient" of the solute [$\sigma = - (d \ln m / dT)$ at the steady state, m being the mean molality of the solute in solution] and T is the mean (absolute) temperature of the system; γ is the coefficient of thermal (cubical) expansion of the solution and dT/dx is the temperature gradient applied (here, $dT/dx = \Delta T / 2a$).

Evidently, the concentration C_0 at the centre line of the duct ($x=a$, Fig. 1) is given by

$$C_0 = C^{\circ} \exp(-a/l) \quad \dots (4)$$

For the convenience of analysis we shall shift the origin, $x=0$, to the central line in the duct (Fig. 2). Obviously, the relation between the x -coordinate of a given point according to these two origins is obtained as,

$$x' = x'' + a \quad \dots (5)$$

where x' and x'' are the x -co-ordinates of the same point according to the previous origin (Fig. 1) and the shifted one (Fig. 2) respectively.

Fig. 2

In the new set of origin the concentration variations at the steady state in the non-isothermal region D of the duct [viz. eq. (1)] are then given by

$$\begin{aligned} C &= C^{\circ} \exp[-(x+a)/l] \\ &= C^{\circ} \exp(-a/l) \exp(-x/l) \\ &= C_0 \exp(-x/l) \quad \dots (6) \end{aligned}$$

(by using eq. 4)

In eq. (6), x is the distance from the centre line ($x=0$, Fig. 2) of the duct. It is to be noted here that the temperature gradient, dT/dx , is unaffected by such shift of origin. Finally, by using eq. (2), we obtain from eq. (6)

$$C = C_0 \exp(-kx) \quad \dots (7)$$

The advantage of such a shift of origin lies in the fact that the resultant treatment becomes symmetrical with respect to the centre-line of the duct and the equations based on this are perfectly symmetrical [equations (9), (11), (12) and so on]. As a consequence, the value of any quantity at points equidistant from the centre-line and located in the hotter and colder parts of the channel respectively, can be obtained by merely changing the sign of the x -co-ordinate in these general equations. Again, the various parameters such as viscosity, thermal conductivity, the Soret coefficient, which are of direct concern for the non-isothermal region D, as will be seen shortly, are taken to be the mean values referring to the centre-line of mean temperature and average velocity. The transformed origin, $x=0$, on the centre-line of the duct is indeed consistent with this picture (see later).

The volume flow-rate of uniform solution in region A is given by $\bar{u} 2ab \text{ cm}^3 \text{ sec}^{-1}$ and hence, the input-flux of the solute is obtained as,

$$J_A = \bar{u} 2 a b \bar{C} \quad \dots (8)$$

In regions A, B and D, the velocity profile is parabolic (vide Fig. 2) and is given by

$$u = A^1 (a^2 - x^2) / a^2 (u=0 \text{ at } x = \pm a) \quad \dots (9)$$

where A^1 is a constant.

The mean velocity \bar{u} is then given as

$$\bar{u} = \frac{1}{2a} \int_{-a}^a u dx = 2A^1 / 3$$

where we use eq. (9).

Hence, $A^1 = \frac{3}{2} \bar{u} \quad \dots (10)$

Substituting eq.(10) in eq. (9), we obtain

$$u = \frac{3}{2a^2} \bar{u} (a^2 - x^2) \quad \dots (11)$$

It may be pointed out here that any asymmetry introduced in the velocity profile, causing the latter to deviate from a symmetrical parabolic shape, in the non-isothermal region D, due to viscosity variations, as well as errors arising out of the use of mean values of various physical parameters such as viscosity coefficient, thermal conductivity, Soret coefficient, etc., in this region, have been shown to be trivial³ (for the temperature differences generally used across such channels) provided that the quantity concerned is ultimately determined by measurements made at points situated symmetrically above and below the centre-line of the duct.

The flux J_D of the solute in region D is given by,

$$\begin{aligned}
 J_D &= b \int_{-a}^a C u \, dx \\
 &= b \int_{-a}^a C_0 \exp(-kx) \frac{3}{2a^2} \bar{u} (a^2 - x^2) \, dx \\
 &\quad \text{(using eqs. 7 and 11)} \\
 &= 6b C_0 \bar{u} (ka \cosh ka - \sinh ka) \quad \dots (12) \\
 &\quad \text{(integrating by parts)}
 \end{aligned}$$

For the steady state situation (which is time-invariant) in region D, we may assume $J_A = J_D$, i.e., the input-flux in and the outgoing flux from region D are equal. It, therefore, follows from eqs. (8) and (12),

$$\begin{aligned}
 2ab \bar{u} \bar{C} &= \frac{6b C_0 \bar{u}}{a^2 k^2} (ka \cosh ka - \sinh ka) \\
 \text{whence } C_0 &= \frac{a^2 k^2}{3(ka \cosh ka - \sinh ka)} \bar{C} \quad \dots (13)
 \end{aligned}$$

The total amount of solute in length L of the duct 2a. b (i.e., region D) is obtained as follows :

(i) For uniform solution at concentration \bar{C} , we have the solute amount Q_A in region A given by

$$Q_A = 2ab L \bar{C} \quad \dots (14)$$

(ii) For non-uniform solution in region D, the solute amount Q_D in given by $Q_D = bL \int_{-a}^a C dx$

$$= bL C_0 \int_{-a}^a \exp(-kx) \, dx = \frac{2bL C_0}{K} \sinh ka \quad \dots (15)$$

The excess solute (i.e., the "hold up") in region D is obviously given from eqs. (14) and (15) as

$$Q_D - Q_A = 2ab L \left(C_0 \frac{\sinh ka}{ka} - \bar{C} \right) \quad \dots (16)$$

Using eq. (13) for C_0 in eq. (16), we obtain

$$Q_D - Q_A = \frac{2ab L C}{3} \left(\frac{k^2 a^2 \sinh ka}{ka \cosh ka - \sinh ka} - 3 \right) \quad \dots (17)$$

Dividing both sides of eq. (17) by Q_A , as given by eq. (14), we obtain for the fractional "hold up" in region D

$$\frac{Q_D - Q_A}{Q_A} = \frac{1}{3} \left(\frac{k^2 a^2 \sinh ka}{ka \cosh ka - \sinh ka} - 3 \right) \quad \dots (18)$$

$$= \frac{k^2 a^2}{3(ka \coth ka - 1)} - 1 \quad \dots (19)$$

Expanding eq. (18) we get

$$\frac{Q_D - Q_A}{Q_A} = \frac{k^2 a^2}{15} \left(1 - \frac{k^2 a^2}{35} + \dots \right) \quad \dots (20)$$

by neglecting terms containing k^2 , a^2 and higher powers of (ka) .

As one might have intuitively guessed, the "hold-up" of the solute is an even function of k , as

is evident from eq. (20), starting with k^2 when expanded as a power series. In other words, it is immaterial whether $(\sigma + \gamma)$ is positive or negative, or whether the hot plate is at the top of the channel (ΔT positive), or the cold plate at the top (ΔT negative) (eq. 3). This, however, assumes that the gravitational instabilities (i.e., density instabilities leading to convective re-mixing in the partially separated zones in the channel⁴) do not alter the steady state concentration profile in region D with either of these configurations.

The magnitude of retention is also seen from eqs. (20) and (3) to depend on $(\sigma + \gamma)^2$ as well as on $(\Delta T)^2$. Let us now examine a few specific cases.

Case I :

For $(\sigma + \gamma) = 10^{-3} K^{-1}$ and $\Delta T = 10K$, $\frac{dT}{dx} = \left(\frac{10}{2a}\right) K. cm^{-1}$ and we have from eq. (3) $k = 5.10^{-3}/a$, and $k^2 a^2 = 25.10^{-6}$. Hence, from eq. (20)

$$\frac{Q_D - Q_A}{Q_A} \cong (25/15) 10^{-6} = 1.7 \text{ p.p.m.}$$

The retention is thus negligible.

Case II :

On the other hand, for $(\sigma + \gamma) = 10^{-1} K^{-1}$ and $\Delta T = 40K$, we have $k = 20.10^{-1}/2a$, or, $k^2 a^2 = 4.0$.

Thus, $(Q_D - Q_A)/Q_A \cong 4/15 = 25\%$, which is a substantial separation.

Indeed, this is the underlying reason for success of TFFF technique in separation of macromolecules. For example, various polystyrenes of molecular weights ranging over 20,000 to 1,60,000, in toluene and a number of related organic solvents have the Soret coefficient (σ) of the order of $10^{-1} K^{-1}$. These have been successfully separated by TFFF using various organic solvents and temperature differences of 30 to 40 K across the channel².

It is interesting, in this context, to note that attempts to measure the Soret coefficient in aqueous systems of Blue Dextran, albumin (bovine serum) and haemoglobin (bovine) by TFFF failed to yield significant retention and hence the desired information². Bonner⁵ also reported, by studying thermal diffusion of Blue Dextran T 250 in water and salt solutions, that the upper limit for σ values of these materials is at least one order of magnitude less than that for polystyrenes in toluene. In fact, Abandanon⁶ has determined σ and the associated heat of transport⁴ of a number of simple sugars (up to trisaccharides) and their various derivatives in aqueous solution and obtained the σ values of the order $10^{-3} K^{-1}$ which are much lower than those for the polystyrenes in organic solvents. It is easy to see in the light of equations derived here that the "hold-up" of the solute will indeed be very small unless the system is characterised by exceptionally large $|\sigma + \gamma|$ values and, in addition, a large $|\Delta T|$ is used in the process. It is possible that such low retentions, reported for aqueous systems, result from the lack of these two requirements necessary to show up the effect.

For the case II, $ka=2$ and the approximations made in neglecting the higher powers of (ka) from the various binomial expressions in obtaining eq. (20) may not be fully justified. Exact formula for retention may then be considered desirable, i.e., from eq. (19), with $ka=2$,

$$\frac{Q_D - Q_A}{Q_A} = \frac{4}{3(2 \coth 2 - 1)} - 1 = 0.24074,$$

whereas the approximations used lead to

$$(Q_D - Q_A)/Q_A = 4/15 = 0.26667.$$

Hence, the approximations and use of eq. (20) are not unfounded even for a value of ka as high as 2.

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